

doi:10.5281/zenodo.20006119

An Analysis On The Effects On Boko Haram Insurgency On Education In Borno State And Yobe State, Nigeria

¹Mansur Shukurana & ²Abubakar Abdulrahman

¹Department of Economics Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

²Department of Business Education Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study was designed to analyze the effect of Boko Haram Insurgency on Education in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria. This research design employed was a survey research design and the target population comprised 71 teachers across six educational zones in the states, with a sample size of 652 selected through purposive sampling. Data were gathered using structured questionnaires and official records. The research utilized a 5-point Likert scale for responses questionnaire. The instrument was pilot tested and the reliability coefficient was found to be 0.822. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages and Paired sample t-test. Results revealed that, Boko Haram insurgency had negative effect on education in relation to enrolment, retention and academic performance. The study therefore, recommended that, government and relevant stakeholders should implement effective strategies to mitigate the effect of the insurgency and ensure the provision of safe and conducive learning environments for students.

Keywords: Boko Haram; Insurgency; Enrolment; Attendance; Retention; Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

Education, as it's generally known, is the process through which an individual develops attitude, ability and other forms of behavior which are important and contributes positively to the society at large (Isokpan and Durojaye (2021). Education enables a child to get appropriate knowledge, value and skills for personal development and national development in general. Peaceful and conducive environment is a determinant for successful teaching and learning as well as student performance (Umaru and Terhembra 2024). The Borno state and Yobe State remain among the states that are less developed in the Federation as their performance in national examinations leaves much to be desired. Refers to 2018 WAEC results, the Borno State came 25th while Yobe state came last, as number 37th out of the 36 States and Abuja FCT and presently the improvement is less.

Terrorism related to Boko Haram is a global phenomenon, and it is ravaging the whole world. It has been defined by Dr. Abdullahi bin Abdul Mohsin Al-Turki (2019), secretary general of the muslim world league as "The intentional use or threat of use of violence by a group or an individual to cause fear, destruction or death, especially against unarmed civilians infrastructure or property in a state. These intended to compel those in authority to respond to the demands and expectations of individual or group behind such violence acts".

Bokoharams is increasing day by day, most especially among youth and adolescents. The random preaching by unqualified teachers has caused a lot of problems in Borno and Yobe state in particular, Nigerian society and international community.

The Boko Haram insurgency began in 2009 in Borno state, and quickly spread to Yobe State. The group is a rebellious one which started an armed conflict on the government of Nigeria. The North East of the country happens to be the base and the citizens become victims of the dangerous clashes.

It has been taken into consideration that, the phenomena of insurgence have been experience in Nigeria since it independent in 1960. Such as the movement for the actualization of the sovereign state of Biafra (MASSOB), “Maitasine” (which was organized and operated as the present Boko Haram), the movement for the Emancipation of Niger Delta (MEND). But the destruction of lives and properties in the present insurgency (Boko Haram) is more than that of the previous ones which also include killing and kidnapping of students’ especially female students, school’s destruction killing of teachers etc.

However, the emergence of Boko Haram insurgency has seriously affected educational system in Northern part of the country. According to the Nigerian education data survey 2010 constant attacks makes it even difficult for teachers and stakeholders to persuade parents to allow their children stay on at schools. In 2014 record has shown that many parents in “Borno and Yobe States” and some Areas of Adamawa State send their children out of the state due to constant and frequent attack by the Boko Haram sects as cited by (Umaru and Terhember 2019).

Insurgency, according to Miller and Mullins (2017), is the illegal use of force or violence by an individual or an organized group against property or even persons with the purpose of intimidating society or governments, frequently for accomplishing ideological, economic, and political reasons. According to Hassan (2014), insurgency can be viewed as a political battle rather than a military struggle and hence not amenable to a solely military solution without succumbing to levels of violence unacceptable in today's global environment. Similarly, Abdu and Shehu (2019), argued that insurgency is a peace and stability Bagaji *et al.*, 2022). Nigeria has witnessed insurgency from this terrorist group called Boko Haram since 2009. They unleash terror and fear in the minds of every Nigerian (Ajah *et al.*, 2020; Nnam *et al.*, 2020)). There is wanton destruction of government properties, the bombing of churches, mosques and other public places, the assassination of prominent individuals, and the burning of schools occasioned by the sporadic shooting of innocent citizens (Atsua & Abdullahi, 2015).

Most of the Boko Haram attacks in Nigeria take place in three north-eastern states of Adamawa, Borno and Yobe (Barnabas & Nasidi, 2022). These states are considered educationally backwards, with high rates of school dropout and low rates of school enrolment (World Bank Report, 2018). (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019). Although the insurgency is currently in a relatively calm state, people are still afraid to engage in their regular educational activities (Abiodun *et l.*, 2020). Some students are especially hesitant to read in class at night when there is an attack or speculations about an attack in a neighboring town (Momodu, 2020).

The insurgent group that has been terrorizing Borno State and Yobe state for over a decade, has launched a deliberate threat against students, teachers, and education facilities creating barriers to accessing quality education in the states (Alkali, Kolo & Hamza, 2020). Their activities have crippled the entire educational sector (Ali, 2022). Insurgency creates insecurity which is a threat to conducive teaching and learning environment for both the students and teachers, academic activities are disrupted intermittently because of sporadic attacks on secondary schools’ education facilities, which lead the government to shut down secondary school education in some areas to forestall sudden attacks on them by Boko Haram insurgents (Usman & Dabai, 2020). One of the objectives of education is improvement in the standard of living of the learners for active participation in national development. In a situation where this objective is hindered by the activities of insurgents, the environment could be not safe for learning (Idowu *et al.*, 2021). The effective acquisition of skills and competencies by learners is predicated on a learning environment devoid of threats and distractions. Such environments encourage students’ motivation and healthy participation in learning, with adequate provision of facilities, a good learning environment should be protected and safe (Okanezi & Obitor, 2023).

The threat of Boko Haram attacks has caused many parents to withdraw their children from school out of

fear for their safety (Amalu, 2019). Additionally, attacks on schools, such as the infamous abduction of the Chibok schoolgirls in 2014, have further eroded trust in the education system and discouraged enrollment. Consequently, school enrollment rates in affected areas have plummeted, depriving thousands of children of their right to education (Tayiimlong, 2021). Moreover, even for those students who continue to attend school, the threat of violence has led to irregular attendance as parents often keep their children at home during periods of heightened insecurity (Abiodun *et al.*, 2020). This irregular attendance disrupts the learning process and impairs academic performance, as students miss out on valuable instructional time and struggle to keep up with their studies (Asiegbu *et al.*, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

The North-eastern part of Nigeria has been under the disturbance of a militant group called the Boko Haram since 2012. The persistent threat of Boko Haram in Nigeria's northeastern region has posed significant challenges to the education sector, particularly in terms of school enrollment, attendance, and academic performance. The problem arises from the targeted attacks on educational institutions and the broader campaign against Western education by Boko Haram extremists, resulting in fear, insecurity, and disruptions within the education system. Consequently, this study seeks to investigate the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on Education in relation to school enrollment, attendance, and academic performance, examining the extent to which these factors are influenced by the ongoing violence and insecurity perpetrated by the group.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study were to assess the effect of the Boko Haram Insurgency on education in Borno state and Yobe State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to assess the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on:

1. Senior secondary school students' enrolment rate in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.
2. Senior secondary school students' attendance rate in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.
3. Senior secondary school students' retention rate in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria and.
4. Senior secondary school students' academic performance in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered:

1. What is the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on students' enrolment rate in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on students' attendance rate on Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria?
3. What is the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on students' retention in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria?
4. What is the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on secondary school student's academic performance in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses were formulated:

H01: There is no significant difference in students' enrolment rate before and during Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria;

H02: There is no significant difference in students' attendance rate before and during Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.

H03: There is no significant difference in students' retention rate before and during Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.

H04: There is no significant difference in students' academic performance before and during Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study employed a descriptive and ex post facto research design, characterized by its focus on describing the impact of an independent variable on dependent variables. Ex post facto, a quasi-experimental approach, investigates this impact without direct manipulation by the researcher (Cohen, Manion & Marison, 2000). The research targeted seventy-one government-owned Senior Secondary School teachers in Borno State and Yobe State as of 2024, spread across six educational zones (Maiduguri, Biu, Manguno, Damaturu, Potiskum, and Gashua), with a total teacher population of 13,026 (9,256 from Teaching Services Board TSB and 1,770 from Science and Technical Board). A sample representing five percent of the population, totaling 652 teachers, was selected using purposive sampling. Two research instruments, a structured questionnaire, and a pro forma, were utilized to gather data. The questionnaire solicited opinions on how the insurgency affected Education in senior secondary schools in Yobe State, employing a 5-point Likert scale. Responses with a mean value of 2.5 and above were deemed agreeable, while those below 2.5 were considered disagreeable. Prior to the main study, a pilot study was conducted to assess the questionnaire's validity and reliability, yielding a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.944, indicating high reliability.

Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics were employed to address the research questions, while inferential statistics utilized paired sample t-tests to examine mean differences in school infrastructural facilities and instructional materials before and during the insurgency.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on students' enrolment rate in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Effect of Boko Haram Insurgency on the students' Admission (enrolment)

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES				
		SA	A	UD	DA	SD
1.	The insurgency has contributed to decrease students enrolment as a result of reduce in parents personal income	316 (48.47%)	270 (41.41%)	37 (5.67%)	20 (3.07%)	9 (1.38%)
2.	The insurgency has contributed to decrease in students' enrolment because of migration	263 (40.34%)	310 (47.55%)	24 (3.68%)	48 (7.36%)	7 (1.07%)
3.	The Boko Haram ideology of Western "Education is sin" and has effect on students' enrolment.	228 (34.97%)	322 (49.39%)	63 (9.66%)	32 (4.91%)	7 (1.07%)
4.	The insurgency has contributed to decrease in students' enrolment because of fear and uncertainty on way to schools	272 (41.72%)	304 (46.63%)	44 (6.75%)	24 (3.68%)	8 (1.23%)
5.	The insurgency has contributed to decrease in students' enrolment because of many school were closed and turned to military base,	257 (39.42%)	305 (46.78%)	41 (6.29%)	36 (5.52%)	13 (1.99%)

Source: Authors' Computation, 2026

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents on the effect of Boko Haram Insurgency on senior secondary schools' enrolment in Borno state and Yobe State. Results revealed that, 316(48.47%) of the respondents strongly agree, 270(41.41) agree, 20(3.07%) disagree while 9(1.38%) strongly disagree that, the insurgency has contributed to decrease in students enrolment as a result of reduce in parents personal income. 263of the respondents strongly agree, 310(47.55%) agree, 48(7.36%) disagree while 7(1.07%) strongly disagree that, the insurgency has contributed to decrease in students' enrolment because of migration. 228(34.97%) of the respondents strongly agree, 332(49.39%) agree, 32(4.91%) disagree and 7(1.07%) strongly disagree that, the Boko Haram ideology of Western "Education is sin" and has effect on students' enrolment. 272(41.72%) of the respondents strongly agree, 304(46.63%) agree, 24(3.68%) disagree while 8(1.23%) of the respondents strongly disagree that the insurgency has contributed to decrease in students' enrolment because of fear and uncertainty on way

to schools and finally 257(39.42%) of the respondents strongly agree, 305(46.78%) agree, 36(5.52%) disagree while 13(1.99%) strongly disagree that, the insurgency has contributed to decrease in students' enrolment because of many school were closed and turned to military base. Therefore, majority of the respondents agree that, Boko Haram Insurgency has negative effect on students' enrolment in senior secondary schools in Borno state and Yobe State Nigeria.

Research Question Two: *What is the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on students' attendance rate on Senior Secondary Schools in Borno state and Yobe State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Effect of Boko Haram Insurgency on School Attendance

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES				
		SA	A	UD	DA	SD
1.	The effect of insurgency has contributed to low school's attendance	279 (42.79%)	332 (50.92%)	20 (3.07%)	16 (2.45%)	5 (0.77%)
2.	Many parents send their children away or leave the state, which contributed to low attendance	234 (35.89%)	349 (53.53%)	32 (4.91%)	28 (4.29%)	9 (1.38%)
3.	The insurgency contributes to late coming to school	212 (32.52%)	365 (55.98%)	51 (7.82%)	19 (2.91%)	5 (0.77%)
4.	The insurgency contributes students leaving school earlier than closing time	252 (38.65%)	311 (47.70%)	55 (8.44%)	23 (3.53%)	11 (1.69%)
5.	The school attendance is low because of emotional instability of the parents, teachers and students	206 (31.60%)	365 (55.98%)	45 (6.90%)	26 (3.99%)	10 (1.53%)

Source: Authors' Computation, 2026

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents on the effect of Boko Haram Insurgency on senior secondary school attendance in Borno state and Yobe State. Results revealed that, 279(42.79%) of the respondents strongly agree, 332(50.92%) agree, 16(2.45%) disagree while 5(0.77%) strongly disagree that, the effect of insurgency has contributed to low school's attendance. 234(35.89%) of the respondents strongly agree, 349(53.53%) agree, 28(4.29%) disagree while 9(1.38%) strongly disagree that, many parents send their children away or leave the state, which contributed to low attendance. 212(32.52%) of the respondents strongly agree, 365(55.98%) agree, 19(2.91%) disagree while 5(0.77%) strongly disagree that, the insurgency contributes to late coming to school. 252(38.65%) of the respondents strongly agree, 311(47.70%) agree, 23(3.53%) disagree while 11(1.69%) strongly disagree that, the insurgency contributes students leaving school earlier than closing time and also 206(31.06%) of the respondents strongly agree, 365(55.98%) agree, 26(3.99%) disagree while 10(1.53%) strongly disagree that, the school attendance is low because of emotional instability of the parents, teachers and the students. Therefore, Boko Haram Insurgency has negatively affected school attendance.

Research Question Three: *What is the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on students' retention in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno state and Yobe State, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Effect of Boko Haram Insurgency on Students' Retention Rate

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES				
		SA	A	UD	DA	SD
1.	The number of students' survival rate is low due to low number of students' attendance which is caused by insurgency.	199 (30.52%)	349 (53.53%)	64 (9.82%)	30 (4.60%)	10 (1.53%)
2.	Boko Haram insurgency has contributed to the drop out of many students	225 (34.51%)	348 (53.37%)	47 (7.21%)	24 (3.68%)	8 (1.23%)
3.	Many parents send their children away or leave the state, which contributed to low survival rate	228 (34.97%)	324 (49.69%)	57 (8.74%)	36 (5.52%)	7 (1.07%)
4.	Insurgency and School Attendance determines the number of students that will graduate	184 (28.22%)	323 (49.54%)	75 (11.50%)	62 (9.51%)	8 (1.23%)
5.	Insurgency contributed to low survival rate because students were considered as targets.	198 (30.37%)	354 (54.29%)	43 (6.60%)	40 (6.13%)	17 (2.61%)

Source: Authors' Computation, 2026

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage of the respondents on the effect of Boko Haram Insurgency on students' retention rate. Results revealed that, 199(30.52%) strongly agree, 349(53.53%) agree, 30(4.60%) disagree while 10(1.53%) strongly disagree that, the number of students' survival rate is low due to low number of students' attendance which is caused by insurgency. 255(34.51%) of the respondents strongly agree, 348(53.37%) agree, 24(3.68%) disagree while 8(1.23%) strongly disagree that, Boko Haram Insurgency has contributed to the drop out of many students. 228(34.97%) of the respondents strongly agree, 324(53.37%) agree, 36(5.52%) disagree while 7(1.07%) strongly disagree that, many parents send their children away or leave the state, which contributed to low survival rate. 184(28.22%) of the respondents strongly agree, 323(49.45%) agree, 62(9.51%) disagree while 8(1.23%) strongly disagree that, insurgency and School Attendance determines the number of students that will graduate and also 198(30.37%) of the respondents strongly agree, 354(54.29%) agree, 40(6.13%) disagree while 17(2.61%) strongly disagree that, insurgency contributed to low survival rate because students were considered as targets.

Research Question Four: *What is the effect of Boko Haram insurgency on secondary school student's academic performance in Borno state and Yobe State, Nigeria?*

Table 4: Effect of Boko Haram Insurgency on Students' Academic Performance

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES				
		SA	A	UD	DA	SD
1.	Boko Haram insurgency has affected both psychological and philosophical aspect of students from attending schools	260 (39.88%)	324 (49.69%)	49 (7.52%)	13 (1.99%)	6 (0.92%)
2.	All the students that experienced Boko Haram insurgencies are psychologically balance without trauma	31 (4.75%)	113 (17.33%)	82 (12.58%)	288 (44.17%)	138 (21.17%)
3.	Government looks warm attitude towards security cause psychological trauma to students not Boko Haram insurgency	24 (3.68%)	59 (9.05%)	125 (19.17%)	295 (45.25%)	149 (22.85%)
4.	Students don't want to be called by their status because of Boko Haram phobia, this has affected them physically, socially and psychologically	181 (27.76%)	334 (51.23%)	64 (9.82%)	57 (8.74%)	16 (2.45%)
5.	Students feel shame, disappointment, discrimination, and embarrassment psychologically for wearing school uniform during Boko Haram insurgency	195 (29.91%)	297 (45.55%)	69 (10.58%)	64 (9.82%)	27 (4.14%)

Source: Authors' Computation, 2026

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage of the respondents on the effect of Boko Haram Insurgency on students' academic performance. Results revealed that, 260(39.88%) of the respondents strongly agree, 324(49.69%) agree, 13(1.99%) disagree, 6(0.92%) strongly disagree that, Boko Haram insurgency has affected both psychological and philosophical aspect of students from attending schools. 31(4.75%) of the respondents strongly agree, 113(17.33%) agree, 288(44.17%) disagree and 138(21.17%) strongly disagree that, all the students that experienced Boko Haram insurgencies are psychologically balance without trauma. 24(3.68%) of the respondents strongly agree, 59(9.05%) agree, 125(19.17%) undecided, 295(45.25%) disagree while 149(22.85%) strongly disagree that, government looks warm attitude towards security cause psychological trauma to students not Boko Haram insurgency. 181(27.76%) of the respondents strongly agree, 334(51.23%) agree, 57(8.74%) disagree while 16(2.45%) strongly disagree that, students don't want to be called by their status because of Boko Haram phobia, this has affected them physically, socially and psychologically. Also 195(29.91%) of the respondents strongly agree, 297(45.55%) agree, 64(9.82%) disagree while 27(4.14%) strongly disagree that, students feel shame, disappointment, discrimination, and embarrassment psychologically for wearing school uniform during Boko Haram insurgency.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in students’ enrolment rate before and during Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno state and Yobe State, Nigeria;

Table 5: Paired sample t-test on the mean difference in students’ enrolment before and after insurgency in senior secondary schools in Borno state and Yobe State, Nigeria

Period	N	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value	Remark
Before Insurgency	12	12091.17	11675				
				3.917	11	0.002	Reject H01
During Insurgency	12	6126.92	11430				

Source: Authors’ Computation, 2026

Source: Authors’ Computation, 2026 Table 5 gives the mean difference of students’ enrolment rate before and after Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria. The study revealed that, there was significant difference in students’ enrolment rate before and after the insurgency because the p-value (0.002) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Hypothesis one is rejected. Therefore, Boko Haram Insurgency has negative effect on students’ enrolment in senior secondary schools in Borno State and Yobe State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in students’ attendance rate before and during Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Paired sample t-test on the mean difference in students’ attendance before and after insurgency in senior secondary schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria

Period	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value	Remark
Before Insurgency	12	12222.83	3407.29				
				1.171	11	0.003	Reject H02
During Insurgency	12	384.750	932.07				

Source: Authors’ Computation, 2026

Table 6 gives the mean difference of students’ attendance rate before and after Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria. The study revealed that, there was significant difference in students’ attendance rate before and after the insurgency because the p-value (0.003) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Hypothesis two is rejected. Therefore, Boko Haram Insurgency has negative effect on school attendance in senior secondary schools in Borno State and Yobe State.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in students’ retention rate before and during Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.

Table 7: Paired sample t-test on the mean difference in students’ retention before and after insurgency in senior secondary schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria

Period	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value	Remark
Before Insurgency	12	8238.50	6212.98				
				2.52	11	0.001	Reject H03
During Insurgency	12	9582.33	22407.98				

Source: Authors’ Computation, 2026

Table 7 gives the mean difference of students’ retention rate before and after Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Yobe State, Nigeria. The study revealed that, there was significant difference in students’ retention rate before and after the insurgency because the p-value (0.001) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). Hypothesis three is rejected. Therefore, Boko Haram Insurgency has negative effect on school retention in senior secondary schools in Yobe State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant difference in students’ academic performance before and during Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.

Table 8: Paired sample t-test on the mean difference in students’ academic performance before and after insurgency in senior secondary schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria

Period	N	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value	Remark
Before Insurgency	12	71.92	13.33	8.554	11	0.000	Reject H ₀₄
During Insurgency	12	33.58	10.71				

Source: Authors’ Computation, 2026

Table 8 gives the mean difference of students’ academic performance before and after Boko Haram insurgency in Senior Secondary Schools in Yobe State, Nigeria. The study revealed that, there was significant difference in students’ academic performance before and after the insurgency because the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). Hypothesis six is rejected. Therefore, Boko Haram Insurgency has negative effect on students’ academic performance in senior secondary schools in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the findings suggest that Boko Haram insurgency has severely disrupted the education system in Borno State and Yobe State, Nigeria, leading to decreased enrolment, attendance, retention rates, and academic performance in senior secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. The study recommends government to increase the level of its security through employing dedicated and intelligent people.
2. Government should motivate the students in affected areas through the award of full scholarship in other to enhance their academic performances.
3. Government should also provide security to government secondary schools of the affected local governments. These will ensure and increase student’s performance and encourage also parents to allow their children going to school.

REFERENCES

Abdu, A., & Shehu, S. S. (2019). The implication of Boko Haram insurgency on women and girls in North east Nigeria. *Journal of Public Administration and Social Welfare Research*, 4(1), 9-21.

Abiodun, T. F., Omolayo, O. O., Tomisin, A. D., & Chinedu, O. C. (2020). Assessment of boko haram insurgents’ threats to educational development in the northeast Nigeria: The way forward. *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 3(1), 31-43.

Abiodun, T. F., Omolayo, O. O., Tomisin, A. D., & Chinedu, O. C. (2020). Assessment of boko haram insurgents’ threats to educational development in the northeast Nigeria: The way forward. *African Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research*, 3(1), 31-43.

Ajah, B. O., Dinne, C. E., & Salami, K. K. (2020). Terrorism in contemporary Nigerian society: Conquest of Boko-Haram, myth or reality. *International Journal of Criminal Justice Sciences*, 15(2), 312-324.

Ali, U. M. (2022). Relationship between exposure to conflicts and academic performance of children in internally displaced camps in Maiduguri. *Frontline Social Sciences and History Journal*, 2(7) 103 -114.

Alkali, I., Kolo, A. G., & Hamza, D. H. (2020). Effect of Boko Haram insurgency on secondary schools’ educational development in Yobe State, Nigeria. *International Journal of*

- Innovative Psychology & Social Development, 9 (3), 154-165.
- Amalu, N. S. (2015). Impact of Boko Haram insurgency on human security in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Social Sciences*, 14(1), 35-42.
- Asiegbu, V. I., Nwankwo, S., Briggs, A. C., & Macs, O. (2021). An empirical analysis of Boko Haram activities on educational development in Northeast, Nigeria. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 5(6), 1376-1379.
- Abimbola, J.O &Adesote S.A. (2019). “Domestic Terrorism and Boko Haram Insurgency in Nigeria Issues and Trend”: A Historical Discourse. *Journal of Arts and Contemporary Society* 4(1), 12-29.
- Akereke (2023). “Effect of Boko Haram insurgency and the school system “. *International Journal of Research in Management & Business Studies* 3(5), 43-55
- Anthony A.A (2024). “Implication of ‘boko haram’ terrorism on national development in Nigeria”: A critical review. *Mediterranean journal of social sciences* 5(16), 31-55 .
- Aro, O. I., (2023). “Boko Haram Insurgency in Nigeria: Its Implication and Way Forward toward Avoidance of Future Insurgency”. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publication* 3(11), 1-8.
- Anthony .A.A (2019). implication of `Boko Haram` Terrorism on National Development in Nigeria. *Mediterranean journal of social sciences* 5 (16), 25-45.
- Awoyemi D. (2022). “Boko Haram, Revenue Allocation and Poverty in Northern Nigeria”,*the Nation*, (Lagos), 12 July, p. 24.
- Bagaji, A. S. Y., Etila, M. S., Ogbadu, E. E., & Sule, G. (2012). Boko Haram and the Recurring Bomb Attacks in Nigeria: Attempt to Impose. *Cross-Cultural Communication*, 8(1), 33-41.
- Barnabas, D., & Nasidi, N. A. (2022). A micro analysis of the activities of Boko-Haram in North-Eastern Nigeria: a case study of Adamawa State, 2009-2015. *KIU Journal of Humanities*, 7(1), 181-188.
- Bankole, O. R. (2021). “Millennium Development Goals and the Universal Primary Education in Nigeria”. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies. An Open Access International Journal* 3 (94), 72-93.
- Danjibo, N. D (2019). “Islamic Fundamentalism and Secretariat Violence: The “Maitatsine” and Boko Haram” crises in Northern Nigeria. *Peace and Conflict Studies Paper Series*, Institute of African Studies, University of Ibadan 1-21.
- Durkheim, E. (2017). “The division of labor in society”. New York, free press of Glencoe”.
- Ekereke, G. (2013). “Effect of Boko Haram insurgency and the school system”. *Journal of Human Resources* 47(4), 991-1022.
- Eze . W.& Agwanwo. D.E. (2023). “Boko Haram insurgency and National Security Challenges in Nigeria”: An analysis of a failed State, *Global Journal of Human-Social Science: Sociology Culture* 14(9), 131-.211.
- Franklin, O. O. (2021). “Effects of Boko Haram Insurgency/Terrorism in Business” *Imasuent E.* (2019). “Insurgency and Humanitarian crises”. *African journal of political social and international relations*. 9 (7) 284-296.
- Hassan, M. (2014). Boko Haram insurgency and the spate of insecurity in Nigeria: manifestation of governance crisis. *Research on humanities and social sciences*, 4(18), 9-18.
- John, D. (2019). “Frustration and Aggression,” New Haven, CT, US: Yale University Press.
- Mare.A (2020). “Nigeria’s interminable insurgency”? Addressing the Boko Haram crises.
- Idowu, B. M., Nwangele, C. N., & Nwosu, C.P. (2021). Implications of the Boko Haram Insurgency for Educational and Economic Development in Nigeria. *African Journal of Terrorism & Insurgency Research (AJoTIR)*, 2(2).
- Miller, J., & Mullins, C. W. (2017). The status of feminist theories in criminology. *Taking stock*, 217-249.
- Momodu, J. A. (2020). Non-State security groups and their role in countering Boko Haram

- terrorism in North East Region of Nigeria. *The African Review*, 47(1), 67-96
- Mohammed, F. J., Abdulrasheed, O. (2015) "Effects of Insurgency on Girls Education in North Eastern Nigeria". *European Journal of Education and Development Psychology* 3(1) 44-50.
- Nnam, M. U., Ugwuoke, C. O., Njemanze, V. C., & Akwara, F. A. (2020). Boko Haram terrorism and human security in Nigeria: Matters arising. *Journal of Aggression, Maltreatment & Trauma*, 29(10), 1257-1278.
- Okanezi, B., & Obitor, W. M. O. (2023). Insecurity in Northern Nigeria and Its Impact on the Education of the Populace. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management*, 5(3), 1889-1894.
- Tayimlong, R. A. (2021). Fragility and insurgency as outcomes of underdevelopment of public infrastructure and socio-economic deprivation: the case of Boko Haram in the Lake Chad Basin. *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development*, 16(2), 209-223.
- Usman, A. R. I., & Dabai, U. I. (2020). Boko Haram Insurgency: Repercussions on Educational Institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)* IV (VIII), 557-562.